

The Influence of Lifestyle, Product Innovation and Instagram toward Online Purchase Decisions (Case Study of Firmi Scarf Store)

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ABSTRACT: The research in the journal aims to analyse the influence of lifestyle, product innovation and Instagram social media on Firmi's Scarf online shop purchasing decisions. This study uses quantitative methods. The population in this study were Firmi's Scarf buyers with a total sample of 85 consumers. The method of sampling is done by using the Census method. The hypothesis test proposed in this study was carried out using regression analysis test equipment and partial hypothesis using SPSS 24. The results of the analysis showed that lifestyle influenced purchasing decisions significantly and positively, product innovation had a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions, and social media Instagram has a significant and positive effect on purchasing decisions.

KEYWORDS: Lifestyle, Product Innovation, Instagram, and Purchase Decision

INTRODUCTION

According to the State of Global Islamic Economic Report (Sirclo, 2020) Indonesia is the third largest developing country for Islamic fashion in the world after the United Arab Emirates (UAE) and Turkey. According to Thomson Reuters, Indonesia is the third largest consumer of Islamic clothing in the world, consuming around 300 billion rupiah per year. Headscarves in Indonesian society especially for moslem women are not strange in today era. Wearing a scarf is a universal obligation that must be fulfilled by an adolescent to the old age. The phenomenon of wearing scarves or veils has developed from religious and cultural movements into a fashion trend. At first glance, inspired and encouraged, many moslem women who did not want to veil, now pay attention to this problem. The increasing demand for moslem clothing has encouraged the growth of the national moslem fashion industry. Along with the development of the scarves and veils, many entrepreneurs make changes to their business. The brand as a trade identity implies business spirit visualization. The reason for conducting research due to the object of research is a researcher business. The object in this study is "Firmi". The word firmi is taken from a combination of owner's name namely Fitri and Mia. Consumers aged in the age of 18 years are more focused on teenagers or adults, especially learning and work outdoors.

Table 1. online sales Firmi's Scarf

Description	October 2020	November 2020	December 2020	January 2021	Total
Total Sales (Pcs)	15	29	17	45	85
Total Revenue (IDR)	1.275.000	2.465.000	1.445.000	2.465.000	7.650.000

Source: Firmi Scarf (2021)

The data table above shows that Firmi's Scarf online shop sales during October 2020-January 2021 increased from IDR 1,275,000 to IDR 7,650,000, except in December 2020, which decreased. The increase in sales occurred due to sales made to people closest to social media, while the decrease occurred because promotions had not been carried out optimally.

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Judged from the phenomenon of the online sales data of the Firmi's Scarf during the period of October 2020 - January 2021, it shows a significant increase, except in December 2020, it experiences a decrease in online sales. During October, November and January, sales increase where the online method is used during Covid-19. This shows that many users today use social media. Social media is one of the effective strategies to promote the Firmi's Scarf, while for offline, the large-scale social restrictions (PSBB) have decreased. In addition, seasonal hijab sales on certain holidays have increased as well.

Based on the results of previous studies, there are several factors that affect online purchasing decisions. Online purchasing decisions are a condition for consumers who want and intend to transact online. Herawati et al. (2019) shows that product quality is the most important variable that affects purchasing decisions, and purchasing motivation has proven to be a good intermediary between lifestyle, product quality, product and price of purchasing decisions variable. Lee & Hwang, (2019) show that the relationship between personal self-awareness and introverted information search is stronger than the relationship between personal self-awareness and extroverted information search. Limpo & Meryana, (2017) finds that there is a significant effect between reliability and ease of use in online shopping decisions at online fashion stores. Based on the results of previous studies, there are many factors that influence purchasing decisions in the fashion industry, such as research by Lee & Hwang, (2019), Limpo & Meryana, (2017) and Herawati et al. (2019), but researchers have conducted preliminary research, restrictions on them. The survey revealed three dominant factors.

This is supported by the results of previous studies from Nathaniel et al., (2019); Kamilah et al. (2017); Hasanah, (2016) and Indrawati, (2015) that show that the lifestyle affects purchasing decisions. The results of Ginting & Sembiring, (2018); Saputra et al., (2015) prove there is effect, but contrary, Maknunah & Laili, (2019) and Hatta et al., (2018) mention that there is no significant effect. The results of Indriyani & Suri, (2020); Suharsono & Sari, (2019) and Fredik & Dewi, (2018) and Astuti & Putri, (2018) reveal that social media affects purchasing decisions. Researchers find indications that lifestyle, product innovation and Instagram social media is a thing that need to be examined, how these variables can affect the decision to purchase online Firmi's Scarf. Based on the problems that occur on online purchases, the results of previous studies, and preliminary surveys, this study intends to analyze an effect on lifestyle variables, product innovation and Instagram social media to the decision to purchase online Firmi's Scarf.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Purchase Decision

According to Kotler & Keller, (2019) the decision is a problem-solving process which includes identifying problems, seeking information, investigating various alternatives, purchasing decisions, and post-purchase behavior due to consumer problems. Purchase decisions are consumer decisions about brand preferences used by consumers. Online shopping decisions are decisions that consumers make on products or services that they buy and consume to meet their needs and wants (Lee & Hwang, (2019); Limpo & Meryana, (2017); Mican & Sitar-Taut, 2020).

Life Style

Kotler, (2000) argues that the consumer lifestyle is a lifestyle where consumers participate in daily activities through interest and consumer income. Lifestyle describes complete humans when interacting with the environment, and personality is a psychological characteristic that varies from people to people. According to Kotler & Keller, (2019) lifestyle is a way of life of someone in the world that is reflected in activities, interests, and opinions. Lifestyle is an activity that a person does in spending their time in a certain environment that is relevant and how they perceive themselves to the circumstances around them (Setiadi, 2015); Andi & Ali, (2019); Haryanti & Nurdin, (2020); Ali & Sohail, (2018); Ramadhanty & Fikriyah, (2020); Nathaniel et al., (2019); Kamilah et al. (2017); Hasanah, (2016); Indrawati, (2015).

Product Innovation

Innovation is organized creativity based on science and technology works to change goods and services for people better than before. Innovation can be a new design, the creation of new benefits, and the use of new technology. Product innovation is the development of original products, enhanced products and brand new through the efforts of own R & D companies (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018). Product innovation is the concept of new ideas, new inventions and new market development (Djodjobo & Tawas, (2020); Nathaniel et al., (2019); Aditi, (2019); Agustina et al., (2018); Ernawati, (2019); Maknunah & Laili, (2019); Hatta et al., (2018); Saputra et al., (2015); Ginting & Sembiring, (2018).

Instagram

Social networks are a means of transferring information between people and groups based on people's experiences online (Gunelius, (2013); Aprilia & Hidayati, (2020); Maulani & Sanawiri, (2019); Indriyani & Suri, (2020); Suharsono & Sari, (2019); Fredik

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& Dewi, (2018); Astuti & Putri, (2018).

Hypotheses Development

According to Kotler & Armstrong, (2018) a person's purchasing decision is affected by personal characteristics such as age and stage of life, work, economic situation, lifestyle, personality and self-concept. There are several relationships between lifestyle and purchasing decisions that affect someone. Among them, lifestyle is a feature of personal factors. According to Amirullah, (2015) every person's activities are driven by his inner strength. We call this motivation as a driving force. There is a person or consumer. Personal strength includes learning and memory experiences, personality and self-concept, concept, motivation and commitment (motivation and commitment), lifestyle. Individual factors of consumer behavior are consumer inner strengths that influence purchasing decisions. This is supported by the results of previous studies where Nathaniel G.B et al., (2019); Kamilah et al., (2017); Hasanah, (2016) and Indrawati, (2015) show that lifestyle affects purchasing decisions.

If a company always creates innovation in product design, consumers can easily find the type of product design they want. Innovation is a creative effort held on the basis of science and technology, which changes a product or service to be something better than before. Innovation can be realized in the form of new designs, the creation of new benefits, and the use of new technology. Product innovation is the development of existing product repair products, enhanced products, or brand new through research and development efforts (Kotler & Armstrong, 2018). Ginting & Sembiring, (2018); Saputra et al., (2015) prove that there is effect, but contrary, Maknunah & Laili, (2019) and Hatta et al., (2018) mention that there is no significant influence.

In today's world, there is a clear competitiveness and insight between the company, and they can enter places where the physical and virtual crowd is concentrated. This is because marketers must use several methods to maintain customer loyalty to the brand, because of the combination of various brand components and traditional marketing that cannot be sufficient in generating income for the company. Therefore, it needs to be explored new methods such as events, direct sales, online marketing and social media marketing. Among various channels, social media marketing has become the most ideal marketing and service marketing platform because of its accessibility and its broad use throughout the world (Kotler & Keller, (2019). Therefore, in addition to its extensive use, social media marketing also provides considerable benefits for companies in terms of social trade and the possibility of minimizing expenses. Social media marketing promotes rapid viral delivery and attracts consumer attention quickly, thus increasing the intention of purchases. The results of Indriyani & Suri, (2020); Suharsono & Sari, (2019); Fredik & Dewi, (2018) and Astuti & Putri, (2018) reveal that social media affects purchasing decisions. With the following research hypothesis:

H1 There is a significant effect of lifestyle on the variables of online purchasing decisions Firmi's Scarf.

H2 There is a significant effect of product innovation on the variable decision to purchase online Firmi's Scarf.

H3 There is a significant effect of Instagram social media on the variables of online purchasing decisions Firmi's Scarf

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH METHODS Research

Design

The type of this study is a quantitative study that uses primary data including literature studies and online questionnaires. Independent variables in this study are lifestyle, product innovation and Instagram social media and its dependent variables are online purchasing decisions.

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Population and Sample

The population of this study is the buyer of Firmi's Scarf during October 2020 until January 2021 which reach 85 buyers. The number of respondents in this study does not exceed 100, so the researchers choose 100% of the population, 85 respondents. Therefore, using all populations without having to attract sample as a unit of observation is called census technique or saturated sampling or census. The buyer's census sample at the Firmi's Scarf is 85 samples.

Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis is the process of searching and systematically regulating data from interviews, field notes, and documents. The method is to categorize data, describe it based on the unit, synthesize it, set it in a pattern, and choose which one to use. Researchers will learn it and draw conclusions so the readers can easily understand it. Based on the research objectives, this study uses data analysis methods and quantitative methods. Data analysis technology using SPSS, or Statistical Package for Social Science Version 24, is an application used to calculate statistics with a computer.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Profiles

All respondents have a female gender of 85 respondents. The largest percentage of respondents' age is 43.5% for the age of 31-40 years of the total respondents. The largest last education was S1 as much as 52.9%. The highest percentage for employment is private entrepreneur as much as 28.2%. The largest amount of revenue is revenue of Rp 2-5 million as much as 43.5%. The percentage residing in DKI Jakarta is 72.9%. The largest percentage of doing twice is 55.3%. The largest percentage of total purchases is 57.6% by buying 1 pc.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Viewed by the results of data statistical analysis with the help of SPSS version 24 the following multiple linear regression results are obtained:

Table 2. Regressions result

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients
	B	Std. Error	Beta
(Constant)	,575	,497	
Lifestyle_X1	,236	,000	,408
1 Product Innovation_X2	,153	,007	,301
Social Media Instagram_X3	,114	,014	,255

Online Purchase Decision_Y

Source: Premiere Data Processed (2021)

$$Y = a + b1X1 + b2X2 + b3X3$$

$$Y = 0,575 + 0,236 X1 + 0,153 X2 + 0,114 X3$$

It can be seen from the regression equation that the effect of lifestyle on online purchasing decisions is one direction (positive). It has a B1 value in the regression coefficient or regression equation, giving a positive number of 0.236. For every increase in lifestyle, online purchasing decisions are increased by 0.236. Conversely, a decrease of 0.236 also occurs in online purchasing decisions if the lifestyle is degraded.

The regression equation shows that the effect of product innovation on online purchasing decisions is one direction (positive). This is declared a positive number of the regression coefficient or B2 regression equation value of 0.153. In other words, for each increase in innovation on a product, the order of online decision making increased by 0.153. Conversely, when the innovation of a product decreases, online purchasing decisions is also decreased by 0.153.

From the regression equation, it can be seen that Instagram social media has one-way influence (positive) on online purchasing decisions. This is reflected in the regression coefficient or B3 value in regression expression which indicates a positive number of 0.114. In other words, an increase in decisions every time using Instagram social media causes further an increase in online

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purchases. Likewise, when social media in Instagram decreases, online buying decisions also fell by 0.114. The coefficient value of 0.575 means without lifestyle, product innovation, and Instagram social media ($x_1 x_2 x_3 = 0$), and the estimated results of online purchases are 0.575.

F-Test Result

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	110,725	3	36,908	106,397	,000 ^b
Residual	28,098	81	,347		
Total	138,824	84			

a. Dependent Variable: Online Purchase Decision_Y

b. Predictors: (Constant), Lifestyle_X1, Product_Innovation_X2, Social Media Instagram_X3

Source: Premiere Data Processed (2021)

F value 106.397 ($F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($n = 85$, $k = 4 = 2.72$), and $Sig = 0.000$ which is a lifestyle variable (F test) calculated based on the results of the simultaneous significance test (F test) in the table above shows that variable X1), product innovation variable (X2), and social media Instagram variable (X3) together have a significant effect on the purchasing decision variable (Y).

T-Test Hypotheses

The first T-test is the test used to determine the importance of the effect of lifestyle on online purchasing decisions. The results of data processing using the SPSS 24 version program are shown in Table 1.2. From the description above, it can be seen that $t_{count} = 5,079$. By using $\alpha = 5\%$ (NK), it is known that the T table value is 5% ($85 - 2$) = 1,988. It is concluded that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $5.079 > 1,988$ or H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that lifestyle has a positive and significant effect on online purchasing decisions, because of the value of $SIG\ 0,000 < 0.05$.

Table 4. t Test Result

Model	t	Sig.
(Constant)	0,683	,497
Lifestyle_X1 1	5,079	,000
Product Innovation_X2	2,78	,007
Social Media Instagram_X3	2,5	,014

Dependent Variable: Online Purchase Decision_Y

Source: Premiere Data Processed (2021)

Then the second T-test is used to find out the significance of the impact of product innovation on online purchasing decisions. From the results of data processing using the SPSS version 24 program in the table above, it can be seen that $t_{count} = 2,780$. Use $\alpha = 5\%$ (NK) to find out that the T table value is 5% ($85 - 2$) = 1.988. Thus, it can be concluded that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $2,780 > 1,988$ or H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that product innovation has a positive and significant effect on online purchasing decisions, because $Sig\ 0.007 < 0.05$.

Furthermore, the second T-test is the test used to determine how important Instagram social networks in influencing online purchasing decisions. From the results of data processing using the SPSS version 24 program in the table above, it can be seen that $t_{count} = 2,500$. Use $\alpha = 5\%$ (NK) to find out that the T table value is 5% ($85 - 2$) = 1988. So, it can be concluded that $t_{count} > t_{table}$ or $2,500 > 1.988$ or H_0 rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that Instagram social networking has a positive and significant effect on online purchasing decisions, because the value of the sig is $0.014 < 0.05$.

Determination Coefficient (Adjusted R2)

The number R above is understood as a value of correlation between Instagram lifestyles, product innovation and social media with the online purchasing decision of the Firmi Scarf, which is 0.893 representing the relationship between lifestyle, product

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innovation and social media Instagram with online shopping decisions. They are very strong. At the same time, to find out the effect of Instagram lifestyle, product innovation, and social media on the decision to purchase online Firmi Scarf, customized R Square is used. The adjustable r-squares ($0.893 \times 0.893 = 0.798$) then 0.790 squared ($0.798 \times 0.798 = 0.790$). The adjusted r-squared number is also called the determination coefficient.

The large small coefficient of determination is 0.790 or equal to 79%. This figure means 79% of online purchasing decisions can be explained by lifestyle, product innovation, and Instagram social media, while the remaining 21% is influenced by factors other than Instagram variables.

Table 5. Adjusted R² Result

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,893a	,798	,790	,58898

a. Predictors: (Constant), Lifestyle_X1, Product_Innovation_X2, Social Media Instagram_X3

Source: Primary Data, Processed (2021)

The number R above is understood as a value of correlation between Instagram lifestyles, product innovation and social media with the online purchasing decision of the Firmi Scarf, which is 0.893 representing the relationship between lifestyle, product innovation and social media Instagram with online shopping decisions. They are very strong. At the same time, to find out the effect of Instagram lifestyle, product innovation, and social media on the decision to purchase online Firmi Scarf, customized R Square is used. The adjustable r-squares ($0.893 \times 0.893 = 0.798$) then 0.790 squared ($0.798 \times 0.798 = 0.790$). The adjusted r-squared number is also called the determination coefficient.

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Table 6. The results of the correlation between dimensions

		Lifestyle_X1	Product Innovation_X2	Social Media Instagram_X3	Online Purchase Decision_Y
Lifestyle_X1	Pearson Correlation	1	.771**	.735**	.828**
	Sig. (2- tailed) N	85	,000	,000	,000
Product Innovation_X2	Pearson Correlation	.771**	85	85	85
	Sig. (2- tailed) N	,000	1	.865**	.836**
		85	85	,000	,000
Social Media Instagram_X3	Pearson Correlation	.735**	.865**	85	85
	Sig. (2- tailed) N	,000	,000	1	.815**
		85	85	85	,000
Online Purchase Decision_Y	Pearson Correlation	.828**	.836**	.815**	85
	Sig. (2- tailed) N	,000	,000	,000	
		85	85	85	85

** . Correlation is Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Data Premier, Processed (2021)

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Variable correlation X1 with Y. Correlation coefficient $R = 0.828$ indicates the level of relationship between the two variables at a very strong level for the correlation interval $0.80 - 1000$. X2 variable correlation with Y. Correlation coefficient $R = 0.835$ indicates the level of relationship, second, the variable at a very strong level for the correlation interval $0.80 - 1000$. X3 variable correlation with Y. Correlation coefficient $R = 0.815$ indicates the level of relationship between the two variables at a very strong level for the correlation interval $0.80 - 1000$.

DISCUSSION

Based on the results of the t-test, the first hypothesis is accepted, namely the online shop purchase decision at Firmi's Scarf is positively and significantly influenced by lifestyle variables. This means that the higher the lifestyle, the higher the online shop purchase decision at Firmi's Scarf. When lifestyle is a characteristic of individual personal factors. Therefore, the individual components of consumer behavior are characteristics of consumers affected by purchasing decisions.

Where Kotler & Armstrong, (2018) suggests that individual purchasing decisions are influenced by individual characteristics such as age, life cycle stage, occupation, financial status, lifestyle, personality and self-concept. This is supported by the results of previous research Nathaniel et al. (2019); Kamilah et al. (2017); Hasanah, (2016) and Indrawati, (2015) which states that purchasing decisions are influenced by lifestyle. This shows that the hijab factor to complement a professional lifestyle is an aspect of a lifestyle that must be considered in influencing online purchasing decisions.

Based on the respondent's description, the majority of respondents are women with undergraduate education, age 31-40 years and income 2-5 million. From gender, education, age and income are closely related to the results of the indicator matrix between lifestyle variables, there are five indicators that have a strong relationship, it can be said that the respondent's lifestyle in daily activities has a professional lifestyle due to carrying out the demands of his work. her appetite for change in terms of age and her desire to look more beautiful reflects her personality to be more confident with Hijab, so that lifestyle influences her to decide to make a purchase.

The results of the t-test, the second hypothesis is that product innovation has a positive effect on purchasing decisions at the Firmi's Scarf online store, and the second hypothesis is accepted to have a significant effect. This means that the higher the product innovation, the higher the purchase decision at the Firmi's Scarf online store. This is in line with the theory that innovation can be in the form of new designs, the creation of new benefits, and the use of new technologies. Product innovation is the originality of products in developing, improving products, modifying new products and brands through the company's own research and development efforts Kotler & Armstrong, (2018) where innovation has an impact on consumer purchasing decisions. The results of this study support previous research by Ginting & Sembiring, (2018); Saputra et al. (2015) who show that product innovation has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions, but according to Maknunah & Laili, (2019) and Hatta et al. (2018), it does not have a significant effect. This shows that the relatively new model factor in the market is an aspect of product innovation that must be considered in terms of its influence on online purchasing decisions.

Based on the respondent's description, the majority of respondents' education is S1 and the majority age is 31-40 years. With education and age, it is closely related to the results of the indicator matrix between product innovation variables, where there are six strong indicators, meaning that respondents' perceptions of the process of choosing a product based on available information can know well the innovations of Hijab products, for example elegant designs with variations that unique, colourful and the type of material used, it affects the purchase.

Based on the results of the t-test, the third hypothesis was accepted, namely the online shop purchase decision at Firmi's Scarf was positively and significantly influenced by the Instagram social media variable. This means that the more Instagram social media publications, the higher the online shop purchase decision at Firmi's Scarf. This is reinforced by Gunelius, (2013) theory that social media marketing is a platform for publicity and communication through social media, using communities that are much more likely to market than traditional advertising channels. The results of the t-test, purchasing decisions at the Firmi's Scarf online store are positive by the Instagram social media variable, and the third hypothesis is adopted which has a significant effect. This means that the more Instagram posts you have, the higher your purchase decision will be at the Firmi's Scarf online store. This is reinforced by the theory of Gunelius, (2013) where social media marketing is a platform for public relations and communication through social media using communities that are much more likely to be marketed than traditional advertising channels. The results of this study support previous research conducted by Indriyani & Suri, (2020); Suharsono & Sari, (2019) and Fredik & Dewi, (2018) and Astuti & Putri, (2018) show that social media has a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions.

This shows that the hijab factor with an elegant design is an aspect of Instagram social media that needs to be considered in influencing online purchasing decisions. Based on the description of the respondents where the majority of respondents have

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education levels of S1, S2 and S3. Respondents at this level of education are closely related to the results of the indicator matrix between Instagram social media variables, where there are six strong indicators, meaning that respondents' perceptions of having the intelligence to see and choose the quality of social media content that contains information about the latest hijab trends, adjust your hijab style according to trends now, share tutorials, consider hijab products, and for hijab can be an inspiration that can be promoted. This quality content can generate interest and awareness and influence someone to buy hijab.

CONCLUSION

From the results of the research analysis, the following conclusions were obtained: 1) Lifestyle influences online shop purchasing decisions at Firmi's Scarf because hijab is a fashion that complements the lifestyle of professional women, so it becomes a strong factor influencing consumers (women) in deciding to buy hijab at Firmi's Scarf. 2) Product innovation affects online shop purchasing decisions at Firmi's Scarf because the models offered by Firmi's Scarf have unique and colorful variations and materials that are comfortable to use so that they become consumers' considerations in purchasing at Firmi's Scarf. 3) Instagram social media has an effect on online shop purchasing decisions at Firmi's Scarf because consumers see elegant hijab products and designs on social media, thus influencing consumers in deciding to purchase at Firmi's Scarf.

This study may have limitations that could potentially affect the interpretation of the findings. The limitation of this research is that the sample used is very limited. Therefore, new research is advised to use a wider sample and a wider range of research subjects. In addition to the limited space for movement (social distancing), during this pandemic the author had quite a difficulty in meeting and interacting with respondents due to having to maintain a distance and also being constrained by the distribution of work from home schedules which ultimately had an impact on the interest and objectivity of respondents in filling out questionnaires. And this study was limited to three independent variables that lifestyle, product innovation, social media Instagram and one dependent variable which purchase decisions online shop.

For managerial implication, Firmi's Scarf online shop should increase the appearance of endorsers and their products in existing content so that consumers can see the product characteristics of Firmi's Scarf. Furthermore, Firmi's Scarf must innovate hijab products regularly by looking at the novelty of hijab designs that are trending among Muslim women, for example by looking at hijab product designs from competitors and conducting market research related to Muslim clothing with the latest models that are in demand by consumers. And, it is better if the Firmi's Scarf online shop pays more attention to the opinions (opinions) of consumers who want to complete their appearance because consumers are more aware of the hijab that is trending, for example by improving future products so that they can increase the choice of existing products.

For further research, it is possible to develop a research model by developing a more varied and larger population and sample so that it can be useful input for the company. In addition, for further research, it is necessary to re-examine the relationship between lifestyle variables, product innovation, and Instagram social media on online shop purchasing decisions with different fashion models. And, for further research interested in the same topic, it is recommended to explore more comprehensive research on the influence between lifestyle and product innovation by making comparisons related to the behavior of other social media users and psychological factors that influence online purchasing decisions.

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